

Experimental Validation of 3D printed GRIN lens for mmWave Automotive Radar

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Abstract—This paper presents the experimental validation of a 3D-printed Gradient Index (GRIN) lens designed for automotive radar applications. Building on prior work that introduced the core lensing elements, this study utilizes a more cost-effective extrusion 3D printing method than the expensive stereolithography process. By employing a smaller unit cell design, simulation time was significantly reduced, enabling a global optimization routine. As a result, the half-power beam width (HPBW) was successfully increased from 50 deg to 139 deg by integrating the GRIN lens, demonstrating its potential to enhance radar performance.

Index Terms—Antennas, mmWave, lenses, Automotive Radar.

I. INTRODUCTION

Biding on safer roads, the European Commission has adopted vision zero and a safety system approach [1]. One of the technologies that has seen rapid development for this purpose is the Advanced Driver-Assist System (ADAS) found in modern automotive vehicles. Vehicles are equipped with different sensors to work with these systems. Typically, Radar systems are used as part of these sensors due to their low cost compared to lidar sensors and their robustness concerning weather conditions compared to cameras. Given the radar sensor's critical role in ADAS systems, improving the performance directly enhances road safety.

The state-of-the-art radar sensors operate at millimeter wave (mmWave) frequencies, providing high temporal accuracy and enabling the implementation of Multiple-input and Multiple-output (MIMO) array antennas for accurate Angle of Arrival (AoA) detection. The mmWave frequency range greatly benefits from waveguide antennas, offering lower losses and higher aperture efficiency compared to PCB counterparts [2]. Waveguide antennas have significantly advanced in recent years, proving a highly efficient and reliable option for radar array antennas.

To further enhance sensing performance, we aim to integrate lenses with the waveguide antennas, improving the overall efficiency and capability of the array antenna [3]. While using lenses on waveguide antennas is not a novel concept, their integration at mmWave has posed significant challenges for automotive applications. In recent years, metamaterial lenses have gained significant interest, particularly Gradient index (GRIN) lenses, which are interesting because they can be fabricated from a single material. Furthermore, this material should be a dielectric, similar to the plastic radome typically used

for automotive radar sensors. This leads to the opportunity to integrate such a GRIN lens into the radome.

In a previous work we presented [4], a lensing method was developed using GRIN lenses with a form factor specifically tailored for automotive array antennas. Despite the promising results and a design optimized for stereolithography (SLA), we were unable to complement the work with measurement results on a fabricated prototype. With the main purpose of the lensing method to shape the radiation pattern, we aim to improve on traditional methods to shape the radiation pattern. The control of the radiation pattern for waveguide antennas is typically constrained by the proximity of mechanical features and the waveguide routing which is present in the same metal structure. By performing the shaping of the radiation pattern of the lens, we can circumvent these constraints increasing the flexibility of the design of radiation patterns and shortening the development cycle, since the feeding antenna can remain unchanged while targeting different specifications of the radar.

In this paper, we build upon our earlier approach and adapt it to be compatible with extrusion-based 3D printing. Although this manufacturing method offers lower precision, we successfully demonstrated that it can be used to shape the radiation pattern by altering the radiation pattern of a medium-range radar to a pattern suitable for corner radars. Here 'suitable' means as broad as possible. To achieve pattern broadening we expanded the Half Power Beam Width (HPBW) from 50 deg to 139 deg, without impacting the elevation pattern. We experimentally validated this by characterizing the radiation patterns and return loss performance of the 3D-printed manufactured lens in an anechoic chamber.

II. FEEDING ANTENNA

As a starting point for the design of the GRIN lens, selecting an appropriate feeding antenna is crucial. At mmWave frequencies, waveguide antennas are widely recognized as superior to substrate-based antennas, offering substantial advances in terms of lower losses and higher aperture efficiency. This is why a ridge gapwaveguide antenna was used in our demonstration lensing method [4]. In recent works, Multi-layer Waveguide (MLW) antennas [5][6],[7] have been presented as the latest advancement in gapwaveguide antenna technology. This novel technology has low losses and aperture efficiency similar to the traditional gapwaveguide technology. Still, it offers higher cost-effectiveness for large-volume manufacturing

Table I: Specification of the feeding antenna.

Specification	Value
Application	Medium range radar
Frequency band	76-81 GHz
HPBW azimuth	50 deg
HPBW elevation	25 deg
Side lobe level	<-20 dB

Figure 1: MLW antenna used as a feeding antenna for the GRIN lens.

and an appealing smaller form factor. As part of a parallel effort, an MLW antenna has been developed. This antenna element is highly suitable for the current work too, as it is specifically designed for medium-range radar applications, with specifications outlined in Table I. An artist's impression of the MLW antenna used as a feeding antenna for the GRIN lens is shown in Fig. 1.

III. LENS DESIGN

As the feeding antenna has been chosen, the next step is to design the GRIN lens. The design approach of the lens follows the methodology outlined in our previous work [4]. However, two key differences will be further elaborated in III-A and III-B. The first difference is that only a part of the feeding antenna is used for the lens design. This allows us to reduce the computation resources needed for optimizing the lens. Secondly, our previous work aimed at using stereolithography (SLA) 3D printing to manufacture the prototype. Unfortunately, this was not an option for the current design. Extrusion printing was employed as an alternative. Due to its lower resolution, the design had to be simplified to accommodate the limitations of this manufacturing method.

A. Unit cell

To reduce the computational burden required for designing the lens, we capitalize on the quasi-periodic nature of the

Figure 2: Unit cell design in CST Studio Suite. (a) Side view, (b) top view, and (c) boundary setting overview. ($r_0 = 0.8$ mm, $r_1 = 2.5$ mm, $x_{lens} = 7.4$ mm, $z_{lens} = 3.5$ mm)

slotted waveguide antenna. As shown in Fig. 1, the antenna consists of five pairs of slots, periodically arranged along the y -axis. The dimensions of the MLW antenna are similar to those described in [7]. For the unit cell of the lens, the periodicity is applied, and the waveguide dimensions surrounding the slot, are replicated as shown in Fig. 2. Moreover, periodic boundaries are applied in the y -direction, as indicated by the orange symbols in Fig 2c. Similar to our previous GRIN lens, the effective dielectric constant is controlled by the infill density of the dielectric material, which varies radially to replicate the profile of a Generalized Luneburg lens. The dielectric material used is the Bambu basic PLA, with a dielectric constant of 2.53 and a loss tangent of 0.01.

B. Simplified lens

As mentioned above, the prototype has been manufactured using extrusion printing. Although a more precise manufacturing process would be ideal for such lenses, the design is quite robust against manufacturing tolerances, allowing us to effectively demonstrate the concept. However, the lower resolution of this method limits our ability to create a highly detailed dielectric gradient. For the unit cell, this results in a gradient that is only controlled with the two radii r_0 and r_1 rather than the 6 control points used in previous designs. Additionally, an absorber is added along the sides of the lens, a common technique to minimize edge diffraction effects in wide Field-of-view antennas. To facilitate 3D printing of the absorber, the Witcom PLA-3D-RAM material is used, with a dielectric constant of 6.3 and a loss tangent of 0.2.

C. Optimization

With all design elements in place, the unit cell design can now be optimized. The optimization was performed using CST Studio suite 2024, which offers several optimization routines. The default optimization routines are the 'Trust Region Framework', the 'Nelder Mead Simplex Algorithm', and the 'CMA Evolution Strategy'.

The Trust Region Framework implements a quasi-Newton method that builds a linear model between input parameters and the objective function. However, convergence was poor, likely due to the system's non-linearity, making it less effective for finding the local minimum. The Nelder Mead algorithm, a local optimization technique, proved successful in effectively designing the feeding antenna. However, while able to find the global minimum, this method is sensitive to the choice of initial conditions.

On the other hand, the CMA Evolution strategy can find the global minimum, even when initial guesses for design parameters are suboptimal. For this algorithm to converge to the global minimum, a larger number of iterations is required. Fortunately, by reducing the computational load through our unit cell design, we were able to perform enough iterations and use this method.

The goal of the optimization was set to maximize the Half Power Beam Width (HPBW) using the parameters r_0 , r_1 , x_{lens} , and z_{lens} . Two constraints were imposed: $r_0 > 0.5$ for mechanical reasons, and $z_{lens} > r_1$ to prevent interference with the physical feeding antenna. Within these constraints, the parameters were freely optimized to achieve the maximum HPBW.

IV. RESULTS AND PHYSICAL INTERPRETATION

After optimizing the GRIN lens within the unit cell design, its performance was evaluated. Fig 3 shows the radiation patterns of the unit cell with and without the lens. As shown, the Half Power Beam Width was successfully increased from 50 deg to 139 deg. The HPBW if taken from the crossing point 3dB below the maximum gain in Fig. 3. Moreover, the pattern remained stable across different frequencies.

For further physical insight into the lensing effect, Fig. 4 shows the power flow at the center cross-section of the unit cell. While the near-field power flow is not directly equivalent to the radiation pattern at the far-field, it gives a good insight into the refraction induced by the GRIN lens. The unit cell without the lens shows stronger power radiated into the broadside direction. In contrast, for the unit cell with the lens, although the overall amplitude of the power flow is lower, the power radiating at larger angles has a larger amplitude, demonstrating the lens's ability to redirect energy effectively.

A. Manufacturing

After validation of the lens design in simulations, it could be integrated with the feeding antenna. To ensure optimal accuracy with extrusion 3D printing, the absorber and the lens were printed separately. For the lens elements, the y-axis of the design was selected as the vertical printing direction,

Figure 3: Radiation pattern of the optimized Unit cell.

Figure 4: Power flow of in the unit cell design in CST Studio Suite. (a) Without GRIN lens, (b) with GRIN lens.

as indicated by the layer buildup shown in Fig. 6. The lens elements were then positioned within the absorber and glued into place.

Fig. 5 shows the complete assembly mounted on top of the feeding antenna. Although the feeding array antenna consists of four transmit (TX) and four receive (RX) channels, only one TX and one RX channel is used for this demonstration. The decision was made to avoid edge effects and prevent the lens performance from being constrained to the specific array antenna used in the test.

B. Measurements

With the lenses assembled on the antenna, the performance was evaluated in an anechoic chamber. Fig. 7 shows measurement results together with full-wave simulations of the lens on the feeding antenna for the azimuth plane. From the same measurements and simulations, the elevation plane of the radiation pattern was extracted. Since there is a difference

Figure 5: Full assembly of the GRIN lens on top of the feeding antenna array.

Figure 6: Enlarged view of the 3D printed GRIN lens.

in broadside gain due to the change in FoV in azimuth, the elevation patterns are normalized to their maximum, these normalized patterns are shown in Fig. 8. As can be seen, the gain is about 5 dB higher compared to the unit cell simulation, this is a result of the 5 periods in the feeding antenna and the tapering in the slots which is present to achieve the side lobe level (SLL) specified in Tab I. Notably, the measured patterns closely align with the simulated ones, particularly for the lens, highlighting the robust performance of the GRIN lens, even with some manufacturing deviation visible in Fig. 6.

Figure 7: Measurement and simulation results of the azimuth pattern of the GRIN lens mounted on the feeding antenna. (a) TX Antenna without lens (b) TX antenna with GRIN lens, (c) RX antenna without lens, and (d) RX antenna with GRIN lens.

Outside of the validation of the radiation pattern, the return loss of the feeding antenna with and without the lens has been measured. These results are shown in Fig. 9. Due to a manufacturing error in the feeding antenna, the return loss for the RX channels exceeds -10 dB slightly at the beginning of the frequency band. More importantly for the validation of the Lensing approach, it can be seen that the addition of the lens has an insignificant impact on the return loss.

Regarding the SLL, it can be seen from 8 that the radiation pattern in the elevation plane is close to the simulated values. Comparing the measurement results with and without the lens, it can be seen that the shape of the pattern in this plane is very similar. The key differences between measurement and simulation are twofold. First, a fast fluctuation in gain as a function of the azimuth angle can be seen, which is not present in the unit cell simulation. This ripple is caused by the diffraction of mechanical components of the antenna assembly. Second, the measured gain is about 0.75 dB lower than the simulation, likely due to the ohmic losses in the feeding antenna and the measurement adapter, which are not accounted for in the simulation.

Regarding the deviation between the design and the manufactured prototype, some asymmetry can be observed in the unit cell of the lens. However, the infill percentage of the structure appears largely unchanged, hence the dielectric gradient remains consistent with the original lens design.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we successfully demonstrated the application of Gradient Index (GRIN) lenses for mmWave automotive radar. Despite the limitations of the extrusion 3D printing method, we were able to refine our previous approach and showcase a robust and effective lens design. The results validate the viability of GRIN lenses for improving the performance of mmWave radar systems in automotive applications, paving the way for further advancements that can surpass current performance standards. This work highlights the potential of GRIN lenses to significantly enhance radar sensing capabilities, offering a promising direction for future development in the field.

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Figure 8: Measurement and simulation results of the normalized elevation pattern of GRIN lens mounted on the feeding antenna. (a) TX Antenna without lens (b) TX antenna with GRIN lens, (c) RX antenna without lens, and (d) RX antenna with GRIN lens.

Figure 9: Measured return loss of the antenna assembly with and without GRIN lens.